

Proposed Marketing Strategy to Increase Sales of Kudimon Healthy Food

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ABSTRACT: Kudimon Healthy Food is one of the MSMEs in Bandung that focuses on healthy snacks. After the pandemic subsided, based on internal data and information from management, Kudimon Healthy Food also faced problems related to sales 6 months ago. After conducting an in-depth interview with one of the owners of Kudimon Healthy Food, lack of knowledge about proper marketing strategies is one of the main problems faced by Kudimon Healthy Food. This could be due to limited time, resources, or accessibility to the information needed. Lack of access to a wide number of marketing platforms and mediums such as large markets and potential customers. This can be caused by limited capital, knowledge, and/or limited human resources. In this paper, the author conducts quantitative research by conducting preliminary surveys and in-depth interviews with various parties as a new potential market segment for Kudimon Healthy Food to achieve sales, Kudimon Healthy Food only conducts Business to Consumer (B2C) sales. The author also analyzes the factors that influence the buying interest of new market candidates Kudimon Healthy Food. The analysis was conducted internally using: Segmenting, targeting and positioning, Marketing mix, VRIO Framework and Business Model Canvas, as well as external analysis consisting of Porter 5 forces, PESTEL analysis, Competitor analysis and Consumer analysis. The results of the author's research, Kudimon Healthy Food can expand its promotion and increase sales ratings in the market place, create a strong online presence and engage with potential customers, Develop an effective content marketing strategy by creating engaging and informative content for websites and social media platforms, Discounts or incentives can be given to customers who make multiple purchases or refer friends to the brand and offer samples it's free to customers, in-store or online, which is likely to increase their trust in your product.

KEYWORDS: Kudimon Healthy Food, Marketing Strategy, Sales Increase

INTRODUCTION

Snack is one of the foods that is often consumed by the community, either at home, at work, or in public places. However, most snacks available in the market contain unhealthy ingredients, such as sugar and artificial preservatives, which can cause various health problems. Even so, in terms of market, Indonesia's population expenditure is almost 50% for food and beverages, and processed food contributes around 35%, so this is a considerable market potential, especially when Indonesia is golden, 2045, our GDP per capita will be USD 23,199 with a population of around 319 million people. The food and beverage industry also has great potential due to its large output as a contribution to GDP. This industry is a mainstay for Indonesia compared to other industries. Various studies show that a sedentary lifestyle and unhealthy diet are the main factors leading to obesity and various diseases related to overweight. That's why Indonesian people tend to choose food by paying attention to the amount of calorie intake.

However, although healthy snacks are increasingly popular, public awareness of the importance of healthy snacks is still limited. The lack of knowledge about making healthy snacks can be an obstacle in marketing healthy snack products. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct research on marketing for healthy snacks that can attract public interest in the right way.

Through this research, ways are sought so that the public can know more about healthy snacks, especially healthy snacks produced by Kudimon Healthy food MSMEs. In addition, a very effective and creative marketing strategy is also sought, good execution and the right target audience, in order to increase public interest in consuming healthy snacks. This research is expected to provide an overview of the optimal way to market healthy snacks so that they can be a healthy choice for the community.

The object of this paper is Kudimon Healthy food, one of the MSMEs in Bandung City that focuses on healthy food snacks. Kudimon must continue to move to compete with other healthy snacks in Bandung. With a strategic location, large capital and sophisticated assets, this research will examine marketing strategy opportunities that are suitable for Kudimon Healthy food whether it can really generate additional sales or not as currently needed by Kudimon Healthy food.

Kudimon healthy food is a business venture that is still classified as an MSME in the city of Bandung that still needs support from various parties so that the products produced can be known to many consumers.

Lack of knowledge about the right marketing strategy is one of the main problems faced by Kudimon Healthy Food. This could be due to limited time, resources, or accessibility to the information needed. In fact, by having sufficient knowledge about marketing, business people can plan the right marketing strategy according to the characteristics of the target market and their business environment. Lack of access to a wide number of marketing platforms and mediums such as large markets and potential customers. This can be caused by limited capital, knowledge, and/or limited human resources. The widespread use of digital technology can provide many benefits for MSME businesses, but suboptimal use of digital technology can hinder the ability of businesses to expand market reach, generate profits, and build relationships with customers. limited budget to finance their marketing and promotion strategies. This can be an obstacle in developing and expanding their business to a wider market. And unable to compete with other businesses then the more competitive the market and the more diverse.

The owner of Kudimon Healthy food until now has difficulty in increasing sales. For the past three years, Kudimon healthy food has not experienced an increase in sales even though it has tried to implement online marketing such as whatsapp, Instagram, market places and resellers. Expanding for marketing expansion which is in the process of curating 13 modern markets in Bandung City. In addition, Kudimon Healthy food also seeks to improve its brand image by advertising testimonials from chefs through the kudimon healthy food Instagram account. Kudimon healthy food also strives to participate in various MSME bazaars and creative markets in the city of Bandung in order to access consumers widely, in addition to widely introducing its products, the owner of Kudimon Halthy food also seeks to participate in MSME bazaars outside the city of Bandung such as in Bali and add resellers outside the city of Bandung. Despite the efforts made by Kudimon Heallthy Food, it involves developing target market segmentation such as young people who like to snack, mothers aged 30-50 years who are on a diet and children with special needs who avoid gluten. This has not provided significant sales six months earlier, it can be seen from December 2022 to May 2023, the percentage of Kudimon Healthy Food sales is still fluctuating, such as from December 2022 to January 2023 experiencing an increase in sales, then February experiencing a decrease. Therefore, seeing this, the author conducted a preliminary study involving 6 respondents from the ages of 24 to 30 for interviews.

Three respondents answered that they had never bought or known healthy snack products because they had never seen advertisements on social media related to these products. Two respondents already know but rarely buy it because it is not familiar and the price is quite expensive. Then finally, two respondents often get to know the product through social media because they feel the product is suitable for consumption for everyone because it offers Health as a uniqueness of the product, but it's just that not many manufacturers sell the product.

As a result, the author identifies the main problem as a problem in the marketing strategy, which hinders the improvement of the desired target market. Therefore, further research will be conducted to determine effective strategies to increase purchase intent among Kudimon Healthy Food's target market using the 5 Why method, Since the problem is a lack of brand awareness among a predetermined target market, the author finds the root of the problem. The main cause is that this product is good and good in terms of taste, affordable price and safe for consumption, but people are not aware that the product already exists and the marketing of this product is not familiar to some consumers. More research is needed to determine strategies so that buying intent will increase.

METHODOLOGY

This research focuses on the Kudimon Healthy Food business. Quantitative methods are used to explore and understand the problem. The research process consists of 6 (six) steps in which the researcher identifies the research problem, reviews the required literature, determines the research objectives, collects data, analyzes and interprets the data, and finally reports and evaluates the research.

This study uses data from questionnaires and other media such as reports (internal or external), books, journals, articles, and websites.

Questionnaires are used to collect qualitative data from individuals by asking open-ended questions to explore their views. The number of participants who filled out the questionnaire was determined based on segmentation criteria from Kudimon Healthy Food. Filling in the questionnaire was carried out in Indonesian and translated into English using the Whattsup social media platform in May 2023 with a total of 200 participants.

Data collected from questionnaires and other media were analyzed into external and internal analysis. External analysis is carried out using PESTEL Framework, Five Forces Model, Customer Analysis, and Competitor Analysis. Internal analysis is carried out using the Resource Based View Model, STP Model, Marketing Mix 7P and analysis VRIO. SWOT analysis is used to find a list of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of Kudimon Healthy Food. In addition, a Root Cause Analysis has been carried out

to identify the true cause of the problem of the decline in Kudimon Healthy Food's income. The QSPM strategy matrix is used to formulate strategies that will be proposed to Kudimon Healthy Food and their implementation plans.

LITERATURE REVIEW

PESTEL FRAMEWORK

PESTEL is an acronym for a tool used to identify external factors that companies face. Characters represent politics, economics, society, technology, environment, and law. All these factors can affect a company's strategy. PESTEL helps companies understand opportunities and risks and approach them in an agile way. It can also be used to predict what will happen to the company and ensure that the company's strategy is aligned with the external environment that has a direct impact on the business. PESTEL analysis is a specific analysis. Therefore, if your company has offices in other countries or regions, you should evaluate the PESTEL analysis. Politics: It's all about how and to what extent the government intervenes in the economy. The political climate of a country (government pressure, monetary policy, etc.) has a significant impact on the companies that settle there. Established authorities increasingly make decisions, both financial (e.g.: fictitious participation) and social (e.g.: unemployment assistance, subsidies, etc.), which can directly affect the day-today prospects of businesses and enterprises. Entrepreneurs who establish commercial operations in countries with constant government conflict must ensure that the needs of indigenous peoples differ from those living in stable and peaceful countries. (Alanzi, 2018). Economics: Analysis using PESTLE provides economic conditions regarding taxes, rates, interest rates, economic growth, recession, inflation rate, exchange rate, minimum wage, wage rate, unemployment rate, cost of living, hours worked, creditworthiness, and availability of financing. Data is generated for economic growth rates. It helps to respond appropriately by providing results on economic conditions and their potential impact on the organization (Buye, 2021). Sociological: Sociological factors, also known as sociocultural factors, are areas that influence people's shared beliefs and attitudes. These factors include population growth, age distribution, health awareness, and professional attitudes. These factors are particularly interesting because they directly influence how we understand and motivate our customers (Vulliamy, S., 2010). In addition, sociological factors are related to social or cultural trends in the geographical location of the region. Technology: The new technologies identified can increase productivity and reduce production costs as technology advances. However, identified changes in the technology environment can present opportunities or threats to organizations (Buye, 2021). Milieu: The environmental dimension includes the natural and physical environment consisting of raw materials, and other natural resources such as land and physical space in the surrounding area. Law: The legal environment in PESTEL includes the laws and regulations of a country. Company management needs to be constantly updated with government regulations because it can affect company operations.

Consumer analysis

Customer analysis is one of the most important aspects of a company's marketing plan. Through customer analysis, a company knows more about its target customers, their needs, and how to develop products that meet their needs. The factors used in customer analysis are behavioral and demographic profiles that determine why a product fits the lifestyle of the local community.

FIVE FORCES MODEL

Michael E. Porter developed leading Five Forces designs and models that have the power to formulate competitive strategies in applying competitiveness analysis to social, environmental and business activities. The five forces include: the threat of new entrants refers to the ease of access to enter a market or industry. With the ease of new entrants to enter an industry, the intensity of competition will increase (Adamkasi, 2018).

COMPETITOR ANALYSIS

Competition is one of the most unavoidable factors in today's business world. Regardless of the size of the company, there are competitors in the industry, and their strategies influence the strategic planning process. Competitive analysis drives organizational strategy and influences how companies behave or react in their industry.

SEGMENTATION, TARGETING, AND POSITIONING MODEL

The Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning (STP) marketing model is a strategic approach to developing market strategies in modern marketing. Focusing on commercial effectiveness, STP helps business owners/marketing teams create communication plans, address rights, and prioritize segments. Market segmentation differentiates markets by following consumer preferences, characteristics, and behavior. The purpose of segmentation is to allow companies to better focus on the allocation of existing resources. Segmentation

is key to differentiation by having a unique perspective on the market. With segmentation, businesses today envision more prospects with high potential (Philip Kotler, 2003, p. 163). Second, targeting is choosing a few profitable segments for businesses with a specific marketing budget to reach. Finally, market positioning refers to the process of forming the image or identity of a brand (product) and how consumers perceive it in a certain way.

MARKETING MIX 7P

According to Kotler & Keller (2016), Marketing mix analysis is a combination of a company's tactical marketing instruments used to evoke the desired response from the target market. The marketing mix contains everything a business can do to engage customers and provide value to them. Some alternatives can be classified into four P's, or sets of variables. Result: Any offers, characteristics, design, packaging, quality and additional services or support provided by the company.

VRIO

Pearson/Prentice Hall argues that VRIO is a tool that can be used to measure internal analysis, meaning that the VRIO framework consists of four questions to ask regarding resources or the ability to determine potential aspects of competition. The VRIO model is used to identify and analyze whether certain resources of the company are strengths or weaknesses (Aribowo, 2021). The four questions include value, scarcity, replication, and organization.

SWOT ANALYSIS

Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats are also known as SWOT. According to Seki and Biler (2016) cited in Ermetin (2023), SWOT Analysis is a methodology used to recognize strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats presented by the external environment of a company, organization, technique, process, or situation. By utilizing this approach, strategies and plans can be designed to maximize existing strengths and opportunities while minimizing the impact of threats and weaknesses, taking into account internal and external factors.

RESULT

ANALYSIS OF EXTERNAL AND INTERNAL ENVIRONMENTS

This chapter will describe the analysis and business solutions to be used in this research. The author will discuss the external and internal analysis of Kudimon Healthy Food. This research will also produce solutions to current business problems.

External analysis Porter 5 Strengths

Porter's five forces analysis is used to determine the competitiveness of the industry, this research industry is the food and beverage industry, especially the healthy snack industry. The following is an analysis of Porter's Five Forces:

A. New Arrivals Threat:

The culinary business is very possible to be entered by new competitors. Because the culinary business is very promising profits, but it must be supported by the right strategy and management concepts for the intended market. Every business person engaged in the same culinary food or beverage field, must be competing with each other to become a market leader. This condition does not corner the position of new players who really want to enter the field. For healthy snack products market can be driven by the increasing demand for healthy snacks as consumers become more health conscious with increasing interest in healthy lifestyles, increasing the chances of new competitors entering the healthy snack market. Therefore, manufacturers need to consider product innovation and creative marketing strategies to maintain place and customers. based on this, it can be categorized as High.

B. Threat of Substitution:

The availability of substitutions, such as the large number of healthy snacks sold in minimarkets, provides many alternatives for consumers to replace healthy food snacks, thus weakening the demand for healthy food snacks. Kudimon healthy food has a fairly high threat because every individual who wants to eat or buy their snacks easily get non-healthy snacks in some supermarkets and shops nearby them. In addition, the many available ptaforms that provide healthy and certainly delicious foods such as gofood, shopeeood, grabfood and so on make consumers easily switch to buying these foods without having to buy snacks from kudimon healthy food. For this reason, kudimon healthy food must always create new products produced from its own recipes, so that if imitated it certainly will not taste exactly the same, and always intensively in marketing and promotional activities. Based on this, this category is called high.

C. Bargaining Power of Suppliers:

The bargaining power of suppliers of raw materials, such as gluten flour, nuts, and seeds and cassava according to healthy snack owners for raw materials is available many suppliers so that it does not affect the price and quality so that it can be said that many raw material suppliers in the production of healthy snacks cause low supplier bargaining power. Based on this, it can be categorized as low.

D. Buyer's Bargaining Power:

The presence of large numbers of buyers with varied preferences, tastes, and budgets can affect the pricing, marketing, and distribution of healthy snack products. Healthy snack companies need to engage with customers on multiple platforms and offer a variety of products to meet different preferences. So that consumers easily move to other healthy food products. based on this, it can be categorized as High.

E. Competitive Competition:

Based on the results of the interview, the owner of snack healthy food said that there is industry competition in the healthy snack market in the city of Bandung. With the existence of various marketplaces and online stores that offer healthy snack options, it shows that businesses are competing in this market. such as, marketplaces like Tokopedia and Blibli offer similar products from different sellers, while stores like ladang lima specialize in pasta, Almonds are healthy, vegan and protein-driven. based on this, the competitive competition category is categorized High.

PESTEL Analysis

The PESTEL framework covers political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal factors that may have an impact on business. Analysis:

A. Politics (Opportunity)

For the Indonesian state, the Ministry of Health Directorate of Health Promotion and Community Empowerment runs the program Health promotion in schools and at work. The health program or movement launched by the government is an effort to improve the quality of public health. Multiple gestures like Healthy Living Community Movement or Healthy Food Eating Behavior can become a successful movement with the support of health promotion. With the movement carried out by the Indonesian government such as the Ministry of Health, it will have an impact on increasing public interest in buying healthy food products such as healthy kudimon.

B. Economy (opportunity)

Indonesia's current strong economic growth is supported by all components of GDP. Export growth remained high at 11.68% (yoy), supported by strong demand from major trading partners. Household consumption improved by growing by 4.54% (yoy), in line with increasing mobility and increasing purchasing power as well as decreasing inflation. This will have a positive impact on healthy food because consumers are likely to spend more money and businesses will get increased profits. This will expand the business to be able to develop even better. However, if the opposite happens then every existing entrepreneur should be careful because purchasing power decreases and adversely affects the business. The positive economic growth rate is an opportunity for Kudimon healthy food to grow bigger. In addition, it is also necessary to pay attention to changes in the country's economy such as the inflation rate and the value of the rupiah because it will later have an impact on selling prices.

C. Social (Opportunity)

Social factors can also have an impact on the healthy snack product market. For example, changes in consumer lifestyles, beliefs, and attitudes toward health and fitness can affect the demand for healthy snacks. In addition, societal trends such as plant-based or non-GMO product preferences can also influence consumer choices. In addition, social media and advertising can play an important role in shaping consumer perceptions of healthy snack products.

D. Technology (opportunity)

The more advanced the times, technological developments and innovations take place quickly and rapidly, so this requires many business people to continue to improve the technology used, if these business people do not want to miss a step from other business people who have used the most advanced technology today. For kudimon healthy food, now it uses marketing through social media and the web and sells its products in the marketplace, making kudimon healthy food easy to reach consumers widely and making transactions more convenient and efficient. In addition, Kudimon Healthy Food has also used delivery via online transportation to provide fast delivery services to all consumers both within the city and outside the city.

E. Environment (Opportunity)

For weather patterns that often rain in Bandung, it can have an impact on the availability and price of cassava raw materials which will certainly affect the supply chain of other products and result in an increase in operational costs of healthy food products. then

the Bandung environment is a cold area and becomes a tourist spot for many people making many tourists from outside the Bandung area come so that it provides benefits for kudimon healthy food owners to develop marketing strategies so that many tourists are aware of the existence of the kudimon healthy food product itself, which means that the cold environmental conditions of Bandung and the number of tourist attractions make it easy for kudimon healthy food to reach broader market.

F. Law (Opportunity).

The existence of regulations in Indonesia related to food safety, labeling requirements, and advertising restrictions can affect the development and marketing of healthy snack products. In addition, changes in laws related to intellectual property or product liability can also have an impact on a healthy snack industry. For Kudimon Healthy, this greatly impacts the operation of its business and provides more value to its products because basically Kudimon Healthy Food is made from healthy ingredients so there is no need to worry about government legal regulations such as halal certificates from MUI, BPOM certificates so that business can run smoothly and there will be no unwanted problems in the future. **Competitor analysis**

The selection of competitors in the competitor analysis is based on the similarity of Kudimon Healthy Food's products and market segments. And this is based on an interview with the owner of Kudimon Healthy Food, there are two main businesses competitors of Kudimon Healthy Food, namely Sagolicious and Ladang Lima. Based on the competitor analysis, it can be seen that, in terms of price, Kudimon Healthy Food is quite competitive from its competitors. However, for sales in the market place, he experienced the fewest sales. Then for the promotion of Kudimon Healthy Food still needs to be developed when viewed from its competitors who have entered TikTok social media where TikTok is among the most popular social media for now. There are also competitors who use Shopee Live, Meta ADS which is a social media marketing that is quite capable of increasing product sales online. Finally, for product results and consumer ratings, it is quite competitive with its competitors where Kudimon Healthy Food has a rating at Market Place 5.0/5.0.

Consumer analytics

In terms of consumer analysis, the author used SMARTPLS software to determine the positive and significant relationship between variables in this study. These analyses include convergent validity, discriminant validity, composite reliability, Cronbach alpha, R square, and path coefficient.

Convergen Validity

The measure used in determining convergen validity is the average of the extracted variances (AEV) across all items in the concept. According to Hair et al (2019), the AEV received is 0.50 or greater, which indicates that the concept accounts for at least 50% of the observed differences in the items. The following are the results of the validity convergence that the author has done for the variables in this study:

Table 1. Convergent reliability results

Construct	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Advertising	0.851
Brand Awareness	0.807
Purchase Intention	0.823
Social Media	0.724
Word of mouth	0.587

Source: SMARTPLS results

Based on the results of the data analysis, it can be seen that all AVE values are greater than 0.50, so it can be concluded that all variables have good convergent validity.

Discriminant validity

The following results of the validity of the discriminatory are as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity Test Results

Construct	Advertising	Brand Awareness	Purchase I	Social media	Word of mouth
Advertising	0.923				
Brand A.	0.663	0.899			
Purchase I.	0.779	0.760	0.907		
Social L.M	0.788	0.670	0.786	0.851	
WOM	0.455	0.445	0.493	0.588	0.766

Source: processed data from SMARTPLS

As seen from the table above, the root of AVE > the correlation value between latent variables (the numbers above), it can be said that all latent variables have good discriminant validity. **Composite reliability**

Table 3. Composite reliability results

Construct	Composite Reliability
Advertising	0.945
Brand Awareness	0.926
Purchase Intention	0.933
Social Media	0.913
Word of mouth	0.809

Source: SMARTPLS data processing results

As seen from the table above, all values are greater than 0.6, it can be concluded that all variables have good reliability.

Cronbach alpha

While Cronbach's alpha may be too conservative, composite reliability may be too soft, and the actual reliability of the construct is usually considered to be somewhere between these two extremes (Hair et al, 2019). Here are the results of the data analysis as follows:

Table 4. Cronbach Alpha Results

Construct	Cronbach Alpha
Advertising	0.913
Brand Awareness	0.880
Purchase Intention	0.892
Social Media	0.873
Word of mouth	0.654

Source: SMARTLPS data processing results

R square

The R square number is used as a tool to describe how much the research model will represent the phenomenon. Here are the results:

- R Square Adjusted (0.494). This means that advertising models (x1), social media (x2), word of mouth (x3) and brand awareness (y) are only able to explain 49.4% which represents this phenomenon. Then the remaining 50.6% could not be represented (excluding other variables that affect brand awareness that were not included in this study).
- R Square Adjusted (0.494). This means that the advertising model (x1), social media (x2), word of mouth (x3), brand awareness (y) and purchase intention (z) are only able to explain 74.2% which represents this phenomenon. Then the remaining 25.8% could not be represented (excluding other variables affecting purchase intention that were not included in this study).

Structural Model

Path coefficient

Based on the results of the data analysis, it can be seen that there are two T statistics < 1.96 , namely word of mouth on brand awareness and word of mouth on purchase intention. And the rest of the five T statistics > 1.96 can be inferred as significant for the latent variable relationship. Then the original sample produces path coefficients with positive values from all variable relationships. Then it can be concluded that there is a positive relationship for the latent variable. So the results of respondents agree that advertising, social media, and word of mouth on brand awareness have a positive effect. And for advertising, social media, word of mouth and brand awareness of purchase intention there is also a positive influence, but not significant for word of mouth on brand awareness and purchase intention it can be seen from the statistical T value of < 1.96 or also looking at the P-value value > 0.05 . So the hypothesis of the result of the submission is Internal analysis.

STP

When starting a business, the STP model helps marketers prioritize offers, create and deliver personalized and relevant messages, and engage different audiences, thus helping to create a marketing plan. STP Kudimon Healthy Food is provided with the following analysis:

Segmentation

Geographic Segmentation

The geographical segmentation of Kudimon healthy food is divided into market divisions into different geographical units, namely the city area. Kudimon healthy food already has resellers in several cities, including Jakarta, Cimahi, but the production location is only in Sukasari, Bandung City.

Demographic Segmentation

The first type of demographic segmentation for Kudimon healthy food is based on people's financial situation, which can be described as middle to upper, or for people with low to middle to upper financial situations. The second group consists of mothers who have toddlers. Health-conscious people, as well as children who are allergic to snack products, make up the third segment. The latter is the group of young adults who have income.

Behavior Segmentation

Kudimon Healthy food has behavioral segmentation based on variable benefits obtained from consuming kudimon healthy food. Kudimon Healthy Food made from gluten flour is claimed to contain protein so it is ideal for people who are on a diet because of its low calorie count. Because it does not contain saturated fat or cholesterol, and almonds are claimed to contain calcium, magnesium, vitamin K, protein, zinc, and copper. This content is able to maintain health and bone density and can help facilitate milk production for breastfeeding mothers.

Targeting

The current target market for kudimon healthy food is women aged 17 – 40 years living in urban areas. They are mothers who have toddlers, young mothers and young adults. Market from Kudimon is middle to upper income individuals who already have their own income. Targeted people usually seek the benefits of such products in the form of convenience, security, flexibility, quality goods, and benefits for themselves.

Position

Here are 9 Points about positioning for Kudimon Healthy Food:

- Target segment: consumers who want to still be able to eat snacks but stay healthy and want to start a healthier life by not consuming products without preservatives.
- Consumer Problems: many consumers want to consume snacks from healthy ingredients.
- Work to do: consumers who need snacks while they relax but can still eat healthier snacks to consume.
- Terms of Reference: snacks that are still good for consumption but with healthy ingredients.
- Basic Requirements: made of ingredients that are low in carbohydrates, sugar and gluten free.
- Unique value proposition: providing healthier food for the consumer's body by maintaining the nutritional balance of the consumer's body. Made from ingredients without wheat flour and made from premium ingredients with different qualities.
- Reasons to believe: judging from the composition of the ingredients used, many testimonials from customers, have received halal logos from MUI and have PIRT.

- Differences with competitors: more concerned with health than taste, can be consumed as much as possible without fear of getting fat when continuing to consume and the cheapest of competitors' prices for the healthy food group.
 - Emotional End Benefit: customers feel safe to consume their snacks and get satisfaction from eating healthy foods.
- Positioning Statement: For people who are looking for healthy snacks, good taste, and quality ingredients, kudimon healthy food is a snack that is committed in the value of health to the consumer's body. Unlike other snack brands, as far as kudimon healthy foods try to be responsible for the impact of what they produce on the health of consumers. **Marketing mix (current)**
- Product: food that has a balanced nutritional content, contains fiber and substances needed by the body for the growth and development process. A healthy food menu must contain low carbohydrates, low sugar, gluten-free, and low.
 - Price: Kudimon healthy food uses **Cost-based pricing** on its products, the range starts from 15.000 IDR – 125.000 IDR. They offer value as the products are made from ingredients that are healthy on the body. They offer health impact value after consumption of their products.
 - Place: customers can reach them through online and offline, making it easier for them to choose which ones they can access.
 - Online through a website or Instagram, which makes it easy for customers to reach their brand because they simply click on the internet.
 - Offline stores, customers can try their products in stores and consumers can feel the experience of shopping on their products.
 - Promotion: they promote their product brand on social media; by participating in events such as the campaign in Bali in 2023, Indonesia Tourism and Trade Investment Expo, KPP Pratama Bojonagara bazaar, participating in the ITB coaching clinic program, Bandung Creative Market 2021 and many other bazaars that have been followed.

VRIO

The analysis of VRIO Kudimon Healthy Food was collected after conducting an interview with one of the owners of Kudimon Healthy Food. Here is the following analysis to determine which resources can create a sustainable competitive advantage. Based on VRIO analysis results that have been carried out, it can be seen that the strength of kudimon healthy food is quality raw materials, closeness to suppliers, and skills to develop a healthy food menu that is varied and in accordance with market tastes. **Internal**

Analysis

SWOT and TOWS matrix

After identifying the SWOT, the TOWS matrix for the business solution is:

Table 5. SWOT and TOWS Matrix

	<p>Strength(s)</p> <p>Offering health with good nutritional content for children, diet people, and breastfeeding mothers.</p> <p>Competitive and affordable prices for the lower middle class.</p>	<p>Weakness (W)</p> <p>Marketing on social media is less than optimal</p> <p>Advertising content on social media is still not attractive</p>
	<p>has received a halal logo from MUI and has PIRT creating a safe consumer experience when consuming them.</p> <p>Good skills in developing a varied healthy food menu.</p> <p>Have proximity to raw material suppliers</p>	<p>The existence of the product is not yet known in all circles of society</p> <p>Sales through the market place are still small.</p> <p>Less attractive packaging</p>

Opportunity (O)	Strategy SO	Strategy WO
<p>Social media can increase product awareness</p> <p>There is a Health program held by the Ministry of Health.</p> <p>Economic growth in Indonesia is getting better followed by household consumption which also improved by 4.54% (yoy).</p> <p>Using market places to sell products to reach a wider range of consumers</p> <p>Bandung as a production house that is often visited by tourists.</p> <p>Abundant availability of raw materials at affordable prices</p> <p>Rules in Indonesia on food safety.</p>	<p>Strengthen promotion with health and consumption safety offerings for dieteous people, children and breastfeeding mothers. (S1, S3, S4, O1, O2, O4, O5 and O7).</p> <p>Making the price not more expensive than competitors. (S2, S6, O3, O6).</p> <p>Create promotions with a focus on the halal logo from MUI and already PIRT (S3, O1, O4, O5).</p> <p>Creating various products with innovative variants by adjusting to community trends. (S4, S5, S6, O4, O6).</p> <p>Offering products to tourists as souvenirs from the city of Bandung by highlighting the health value in it (S1, S3, S4, S5, O2, O3, O5, O7).</p>	<p>Strengthening promotion through social media such as TikTok, Instagram and other social media to increase awareness of this product. (W1,W2, W3, O1, O5)</p> <p>Create engaging content with a focus on Health values. (W3, O1, O2, O5, O7)</p> <p>Developing market reach through online and offline promotions in tourist attractions by campaigning for healthy living to generate attention and attract consumer interest (W1, W2, W3, O1, O2, O3, O5, O7)</p> <p>Making various levels of society to shop through their online stores in order to strengthen product ratings in the market place. (W3, W4, O2,O4)</p> <p>Create attractive and practical packaging by highlighting product safety that builds consumer interest in buying it. (W5, O6, O7).</p>
Threat (T)	Strategy ST	Strategy WT
<p>Business capital that is not large makes it easier for many newcomers in this industry</p> <p>Changes in people's trends related to their preferences in choosing food.</p> <p>The number of healthy snacks sold in minimarkets provides an alternative for consumers to move from kudimon healthy food.</p> <p>Many healthy foods are sold online with a variety of flavors and are innovative in terms of taste and packaging.</p> <p>Competitive competition both offline and online.</p>	<p>Enriching products by introducing new variants with various content in it. (S1, S3, S5, T1, T2, T3, T4, T5)</p> <p>Emphasis by highlighting the distinctiveness of taste with nutritional content and clean and hygienic manufacturing process. (S1, S5, T1, T2, T3, T4, T5)</p> <p>Emphasis on cheaper prices compared to existing competitors. (S2, S6, T1, T4, T5)</p>	<p>Budgeting funds to strengthen online marketing with interesting content is one of the focuses for the future. (W1, W2, T4, T5)</p> <p>Promoting product variants by highlighting attractive packaging both online and offline. (W1, W2, W5, T2, T3, T4, T5)</p> <p>Strengthen online store ratings and reviews from consumers related to products by offering discounts for consumers who review products in online stores. (W3, W4, T3, T4, T5)</p>

Source: Author Analysis

Table VI.12 Strategy Alternatives Ranking

	Strategy Description	Rank	QSPM Score
WO2	Create engaging content with a focus on Health values	1	6,89
SO1	Strengthen promotion with health and consumption safety offerings for dietees, children and breastfeeding mothers	2	6,62
WT3	Strengthen online store ratings and reviews from consumers related to products by offering discounts for consumers who review products in online stores.	3	4,74
ST1	Enriching products by introducing new variants with various content in them	4	4,72

Source: QSPM Result

After conducting a QSPM analysis, it is determined by identifying alternative strategies that obtain the highest score and ranking. A higher score signifies the preferred option for implementation. Conversely, a low score indicates that a particular approach is unfair and unworthy of adoption by the company.

Business solutions

The author must now be able to develop these solutions to overcome these obstacles and determine the optimal sequence or strategic priorities that can be applied in the near future.

- Create engaging content with a focus on Health values
- Strengthen promotion with health and consumption safety offerings for dietees, children and breastfeeding mothers.
- Strengthen online store ratings and reviews from consumers related to products by offering discounts for consumers who review products in online stores.
- Enriching products by introducing new variants with various content in them

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research, there are several factors that can influence **Kudimon Healthy Food's** purchase intention to increase its sales volume.

- Social Media Marketing Positively Affects Brand Awareness
- Advertising has a positive influence on Brand Awareness
- Word of Mouth has a positive influence on Brand Awareness
- Social Media Marketing Positively Affects Purchase Intention
- Word of Mouth positively affects Purchase Intention
- Advertising has a positive effect on Purchase Intention
- Brand Awareness has a positive effect on Purchase Intention

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